

Investigation on the Effects of Humidity and High Temperature on the NH_2 -content of Different Samples of Rice.

BY N. M. BASU AND S. R. MAITRA.

As rice stored up in dark, dingy go-downs during the rainy season when air is saturated with moisture at high temperature, becomes unhealthy and is believed to be one of the potent factors in the production of epidemic dropsy and since it is known that some amines, especially histamine, cause capillary dilatation leading to dropsy, which is the most prominent symptom of this disease, we thought that some amines might be produced in rice under this condition. Now if amines be actually produced in rice under these conditions, there would necessarily be an increase in its NH_2 -content, although an increase in NH_2 -content may not prove the formation of these poisonous amines. We accordingly wanted to see whether there is an increase in the NH_2 -content of different samples of rice under these conditions, for if there be no increase in the NH_2 -content, we may conclude that amines are also not produced.

Various samples of rice freshly milled by indigenous method (*Dhenki-chata chal*) were obtained from Burdwan and fresh samples of milled rice from the College Street Market in Calcutta. They were kept in dry dishes in an incubator along with a dish of water so that the air inside was saturated with moisture and the temperature of the incubator was kept constant at 92°F . The samples of rice thus treated were examined, after every 4 or 5 days for a long period for their $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ content by Van Slyke's method which has been slightly modified as given below.

EXPERIMENTAL.

As the method of making a dispersion of rice-powder for estimation of $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ in Van Slyke's apparatus has been arrived at after a good deal of experimentation, it is worth while giving a resumé of the various preliminary attempts.

A suspension of rice-powder in normal saline was tried first but uniform results were not obtained owing to deposition of rice-powder in the reaction vessel and excessive frothing even in the presence of caprylic alcohol or liquid paraffin. The extract of the proteins of rice

with 10% salt solution was next tried but the results were too low and the residue also contained protein. As rice contains considerable amount of glutaline (alkali soluble) and small amounts of alcohol-soluble prolamine, saline extract can never completely remove the proteins from rice. A dispersion of rice-powder in honey was subsequently tried but the results were not consistent as honey contains variable amounts of $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$; gum-acacia was then used for making a dispersion of rice-powder, but the frothing was excessive and troublesome. The results were constant if the froth were taken to the Hempel pipette 2 or 3 times for absorption, caprylic alcohol were added once more after the first transference of the gas to the Hempel pipette and the shaking of the reaction vessel were done twice. Next the dispersion of rice-powder in dextrin solution was tried, and the results obtained were constant. There was practically no frothing so that caprylic alcohol need not be added more than once.

FIG. I.

Procedure.

The gas burette F in Van Slyke's macro-apparatus is filled with water and the de-aminising bulb and the tube attached thereto are freed from air and filled with nitric oxide as is done in Van Slyke's method, the passage in the stop-cock connecting B and D being filled with NaNO₂ mixture. About 1 c. c. of caprylic alcohol is then carefully taken into D from B so as to avoid air bubbles. Now 2 grams of finely powdered rice are weighed accurately in a weighing bottle and transferred completely with a little 10% dextrin solution to an agate mortar in which the dispersion of rice-powder is made with the pestle by the addition of suitable amounts of dextrin solution. This dispersion is then transferred through a funnel to B of a micro-apparatus* and thence to D. The mortar, pestle and the funnel are now washed down with dextrin solution to B and then transferred to D, care being taken to prevent air bubbles from going inside D. The reaction vessel is now shaken for three minutes. The tap 'a', is then turned on for a while so that the liquid rises in D upto a little below the bulb at the top of D for the transference of the major part of gas from D to F. The gas in F is then transferred to Hempel pipette. The connection between D and F is again restored. The reaction vessel is shaken once more for three minutes. The gas is now transferred to F with as much frothing as is possible by turning on a. The gas is once more removed to Hempel pipette which is then shaken for one minute. The

* We were using micro-apparatus at the beginning but owing to the following difficulties we selected the reaction vessel of the macro-apparatus and the gas burette of the micro-apparatus to which 2 bulbs of 50 c. c. each were attached :—

(i) The junctional tube between B and D in the micro-apparatus being very narrow, the thick colloidal dispersion of rice in dextrin solution cannot readily pass through to the de-aminising bulb. In the macro-apparatus this part is sufficiently wide.

(ii) De-aminising bulb in the macro-apparatus being much bigger, more space is obtained for the reaction to take place of a rather large volume of rice dispersion and accordingly the reaction is completed more readily.

(iii) The graduations in the burette of the macro-apparatus are not sufficiently fine and accordingly small differences in the volume of nitrogen which are generally noted in our estimations, cannot be detected. In the micro-apparatus these graduations are much finer and therefore answer our purpose very well. But the volumes of gases, i.e., NO or N₂ accumulating in D and F become so large that these gases may escape by driving out the whole of water in the burette. To prevent this, two additional bulbs were attached in succession to the end of the burette F and connected by a rubber tube to the reservoir.

remaining gas is next returned to F. As the gas that has collected in the meantime in D may contain a trace of nitrogen, it is once more transferred to F and thence to Hempel pipette which is again shaken for one minute. The remaining gas is then returned to F and the reading is taken. After about fifteen minutes the reading is once more taken and the volume obtained in the second reading is corrected to N. T. P.

Results.—Four samples of milled rice and an equal number of *Dhenki*-hulled rice were examined for their $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ content at varying intervals after they were kept in the incubator. The results of these analysis are recorded in Table I and II. The figures in the tables refer to c.c. of nitrogen corrected to N. T. P. per g. of rice.

TABLE I.

Milled rice.

Sample A.		Sample B.		Sample C.		Sample D.	
$\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ content.	No. of days.	$\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ content	No. of days.	$\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ content.	No. of days.	$\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ content.	No. of days.
2.48	Normal*	2.24	Normal*	2.18	Normal*	2.28	Normal
2.3	After 6 days	2.28	After 7 days	2.32	After 6 days	2.42	After 3 days
2.6	10	2.3	12	2.38	11	2.62	7
2.7	15	2.24	15	2.46	14	2.62	10
2.2	19	2.5	19	2.18	18	2.56	13
						2.5	18
						2.48	19

TABLE II.

Dhenki-hulled rice.

Sample I.		Sample II.		Sample III.		Sample IV.	
$\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ content.	No. of days.						
2.3	Normal*	2.12	Normal*	2.58	Normal*	2.6	Normal*
2.32	After 6 days	2.28	After 7 days	2.6	After 6 days	2.6	After 3 days
2.3	10	2.5	12	2.62	11	2.62	7
2.34	15	2.3	15	2.62	14	2.62	10
2.24	19	2.3	19	2.48	18	2.78	13
						2.72	18
						2.7	19

DISCUSSION.

From Tables I and II it appears that in samples B, C of milled rice and I, II, and III of *Dhenki*-hulled rice there is a gradual increase in $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$, the longer the sample is kept in the thermostat, although this increase is much less marked in the case of *Dhenki*-hulled rice.

* Before these were kept in the incubator.

It further appears that the amino-nitrogen having increased to a considerable extent, begins to fall abruptly.

In the case of sample A, there is a fall in the amount of nitrogen at the outset, then a rise which is followed by a diminution as in the case of other samples.

It is obvious that the rise in amino-nitrogen is due to the gradual decomposition of proteins of rice resulting in the formation of substances containing NH₂-radical. Whether these latter include amines or not, we cannot at present say definitely, for we have not as yet investigated that point. The subsequent fall in amino-nitrogen is probably due to the conversion of NH₂-radical into NH₃ and the liberation of the latter into air.

The peculiar behaviour of sample A may be due to the peculiar condition of this rice while it was under investigation. This rice appears to have been disintegrated and perforated, *i.e.*, the frame work has been already decomposed. Accordingly, substances containing NH₂-group have been already formed. When, therefore, it was placed in the thermostat in a moist atmosphere, NH₂ radical was soon converted into NH₃ and disappeared, resulting in a fall in amino-nitrogen after a few days. New surfaces within the rice were then exposed to the humid atmosphere; there was, therefore, further decomposition, resulting in an increase in amino-nitrogen. There would naturally be again a fall in amino-nitrogen owing to aforementioned reasons.

CONCLUSIONS.

It may be concluded that rice is decomposed in the rainy season with the production of substances containing NH₂-radical. Whether amines are formed we cannot at present definitely say. Further, Dhenki-hulled rice shows greater resistance to the action of humid atmosphere and high temperature than milled rice. This conclusion is corroborated by the following two facts we noticed. First, milled rice, after being exposed to humid atmosphere at a high temperature, can be more easily powdered than Dhenki-hulled rice. Secondly, it is very curious that in all bottles containing milled rice, some organism have grown, whereas these are absent in bottles containing Dhenki-hulled rice.

PHYSIOLOGICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

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